

IMPROVING THE DEVELOPMENT OF FINANCIAL AND LEGAL INSTITUTIONS

Abdurauf Abdullayev

Professor of the Department of "Organization and Management of Production",

Doctor of Economics, Andijan Engineering Institute

Abstract: All the activities of the state are connected with finance. Their importance has especially increased in connection with the acquisition of state sovereignty of the Republic of Uzbekistan and when the society focused on the formation of a market economy, free movement of goods, services and financial resources, support for competition and freedom of economic activity. Constitutional recognition and State protection of all forms of property have become more important than ever.

Keywords: employee, financial relations, financial reporting, organizational support, statistics, control, audit.

Introduction. Through finance, direct and inverse connections are made in economic, social and political systems and processes.

Any decision of the state is considered real only after finding the possibility of covering the costs associated with its implementation with monetary resources. The budget is the main part of financial relations that expresses the material mediation of the functioning of the state, either at the expense of centralized extra-budgetary funds, or at the expense of decentralized financial resources, the role of which has greatly increased in recent years.

Finance performs three functions: distribution, control and incentive, the role of which is increasingly increasing at the present stage. The manifestation of these functions is possible only if their legal regulation and legal support are improved. The relevance may become more acute if we take into account that the stimulating function of finance as an independent one has been singled out only recently, and it can actually manifest itself only with an adequate ratio of cost, material, and price indicators.

The successful development of macroeconomics presupposes the establishment of not only direct, but also inverse links between the functions of distribution, control and incentive provided by law. Moreover, these connections are very complex, since the distribution itself already provides not only the function of control, but also the tracking of money over the course of economic and social development in the state.

Financial resources are objectively not unlimited, so the relations on the distribution and redistribution of the national income of the country are under the constant control of the state, and this influence is legal. Hence, the constant improvement of legal norms in the field of financial activities of the state is always relevant, but today, in a market economy, it is especially important.

A well-developed and well-established financial and credit mechanism is needed. The object of regulation of lending, the impact of which is the monetary funds of the state.

The relevant regulatory system should be based on certain general principles underlying financial law, which, in turn, should form the basis of financial legislation. Of course, the reverse effect of financial legislation on financial law as an independent branch of the entire legal system is also obvious.

It is relevant that the development of financial and legal institutions is directly related to the satisfaction of the entire hierarchy of interests: actually state, state-public, collective and personal, including private property, which at the present stage, due to the need for the state to implement social programs, are interconnected and mutually conditioned, which is expressed in the increasing interdependence of the state's financial resources with each other and with material resources.

The state, regulating financial and credit relations with the help of legal norms, ensures the solution of the following tasks::

1. Public administration is directly carried out: in particular, in accordance with the budget, the state allocates funds to finance the performance of its tasks and functions. Naturally, the area of the economy where more funds are allocated is developing successfully. Funds of money as a management tool in the hands of the state are efficient, mobile, amenable to accurate accounting and calculations, well redistributed, regulated.

2. Finance and credit make it possible to ensure an effective system of direct and reverse relations in the state, and it will function more effectively the better its foundations are legally regulated. So, each state allocation should give a calculated return. The expected end result should be achieved for each area and direction of the state's activity.

With the help of finance and financial law, this is achieved in the following way: for example, centralized allocations in the economy should actually be used for the needs of scientific and technological progress, for the maintenance and development of priority sectors of the economy and social policy of the state. As a result, the economy as a whole should produce greater returns, either by increasing profits or by reducing production costs.

The redistributed part, in particular through taxes, of the total social product

goes to the state budget, thereby increasing the public consumption funds. Here we should immediately draw attention to the fact that the norm of tax law, being a norm of financial and legal law, serves as an exceptionally powerful stimulating means of state influence on society. In turn, an increase (or decrease) in budget revenues entails more or less successful financing of the social sphere. Here there is a direct link with all spheres of state activity in the allocation of funds and a feedback link in the accumulation of a part of the total social product in the funds of monetary funds. By the way, the accumulation of funds in decentralized funds and their spending also serve as a direct and feedback link in public administration, but they are much more complicated.

If the budget allocations, which represent direct connections, do not give sufficient returns, then the budget replenishment will be less than planned, and this will immediately affect the state of the economy and the state as a whole. The improvement of the financial situation is primarily due to the elimination of the budget deficit.

The correct use and improvement of legislation in the field of financial regulation should serve the purposes of improving the integration processes in the state, which are manifested in comprehensive programs. Thus, when studying the development of local finance and local self-government bodies, it is important not to lose sight of the fact that in order to carry out their functions, in particular, the integrated development of macroeconomics at local levels, and the effective exercise of their powers, they must increasingly make full use of financial resources, both centralized (redistributed from higher budgets, transfers) and decentralized, formed in their territories.

On the one hand, the use of all these means ensures that local self-government bodies fully exercise their competence, on the other hand, a system of direct and feedback links is provided in the implementation of all the tasks facing the state, only on a larger scale and more complex interdependencies.

Various complications and non-standard situations are possible, when finance must immediately respond, give a signal (information) to the governing bodies about any imbalances and violations in the performance of its tasks. By the way, these signals come quite objectively. So, the crisis of non-payments, leading to disastrous socio-economic consequences, is, as already mentioned, a feedback signal with a minus sign. In the normal development of the situation, the higher state bodies should immediately make corrective management decisions with the help of finance, direct them to increase or decrease the volume of financing and lending, change the forms of payments of producers and buyers, so that the debt on non-payments and wages does not grow.

In the norms of law, general principles should be laid down, which, if

necessary, work automatically, with good work, financial funds increase, with bad work-decreases, and this, in turn, objectively affects a particular state of society and the state. The need to consolidate in the general, uniform rules of financial law the systemic links and interdependencies in the financial activities of the state is obvious, since this reflects all the processes taking place in society and the state. This will serve as a guarantee, on the one hand, of centralized financial and planned state management of economic, social and political processes, and on the other hand, it will allow for management through a market mechanism.

Financial law regulates public relations that develop in the process of financial activity of the state, and its norms are always associated with the regulation of relations regarding the distribution of public product and national income in monetary form.

According to the method of legal regulation, financial law, at first glance, completely coincides with administrative law, the same method of power regulations, inequality of subjects of legal relations. However, administrative law does not regulate financial relations, the specifics of which dictate the need to apply a special financial and legal method. Most of the regulations in such cases come from the financial and credit authorities of the state, created specifically for the implementation of financial activities, and these bodies are connected with other state bodies only functionally through financial activities. There is no complete subordination here, as is observed in other branch management. In this regard, the degree of imperativeness of the norms is also different, and there are features of the expression of economic management methods in them. An example of this is the bank's credit sanctions.

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